

Speciation studies of binary complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with L-proline in 1,2-propanediol-water mixtures

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Abstract : Chemical speciation of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of L-proline in 0.0–60.0% v/v 1,2-propanediol-water mixtures maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L⁻¹ at 303.0 K has been studied pH metrically. The active forms of ligand are LH₂⁺, LH and L⁻. The predominant species detected are ML, MLH and ML₂. Models containing different number of species were refined by using the computer program MINIQUAD75. The best-fit chemical models were arrived at based on statistical parameters. The trend in variation of complex stability constants with change in the dielectric constant of the medium is explained on the basis of electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces.

Keywords : Complex equilibria, chemical speciation, L-proline, 1,2-propanediol.

Introduction

Metal complexes with amino acids play important role in various biological systems. Hence the formation, stability and reactivity of these complexes have been an active field of research^{1,2}. Transition metal ion chelate complexes are also exploited by industry in the large-scale purification of α -amino acids and a wide range of drug and drug precursors containing an amino carboxylic acid moiety^{3,4}. Amino acids are important low molecular weight ligands in humans^{5–8} and other biosystems^{9,10}. Their involvement in Cu^{II} transport and metabolism is well-documented^{11,12}. In addition, the reactivity of amino acids is often modified when they are coordinated to metal ions. Nature exploits this effect through the construction of metal-ion binding cavities within the active sites of many enzymes that serve to accelerate reactions that would otherwise proceed too slowly to be useful in living systems.

L-Proline is an imino acid containing pyrrole type nitrogen rather than the amino nitrogen of the amino acids¹³. It has several significant applications in biological systems^{14–16} and it may be used to reduce the level of toxicity of metals like Co^{II} in the biological systems¹⁷. It is a bidentate ligand with a high affinity to metals like

Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}. Formation of binary complexes of L-proline with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} were reported earlier, using paper electrophoretic technique¹⁷, batch equilibrium method with cation exchange resin¹⁸ and potentiometric titration methods¹⁹. Stability constants were determined by Irving and Rossotti technique²⁰ and evaluated with the computer program SCOGS²¹. Temperature dependence of the stability constants of L-proline with Cu^{II} was also reported^{22,23}.

1,2-Propanediol also known as propylene glycol (PG) is a clear, viscous, colorless, odorless liquid with a dielectric constant of 30.2²⁴. It is fully miscible with water. The dielectric constant of the medium decreases with increase in mole fraction of PG.

Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} are associated with several enzymes^{25,26} and any variation in their concentration leads to metabolic disorders²⁷. Hence, the speciation studies of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of L-proline in varying compositions of PG-water mixtures have been carried out.

Results and discussion

The relation between the formation function \bar{n} (average number of moles of ligand bound per mole of metal

ions) and pL (negative logarithm of ligand concentration) gives some information regarding the existence of protonated species. Overlapping formation curves for different concentrations of the ligand for the same metal ion concentration infer the existence of only unprotonated metal-ligand complexes. But the spread in formation curves suggests the possible coexistence of protonated and unprotonated species. The non-overlapping formation curves (Fig. 1) indicate the existence of protonated species. Under the present experimental conditions, the predominant forms of the ligand are LH_2^+ and LH , which

limit the probable metal-ligand species to be ML , ML_2 , MLH , ML_2H_2 and ML_2H . Exhaustive modeling was performed for Co^{II} -L-proline system in 40% v/v PG-water mixture and the results are given in Table 1. The models indicated better statistics as the number of species was increased, confirming better fit. There was no further improvement in the fit on inclusion of some more species in the model containing ML , ML_2 and MLH . This indicates that the exhaustive model appropriately fit the experimental data. Such exhaustive modeling was performed for all the systems. The results of the best fit models that contain the stoichiometry of the complex species and their overall formation constants along with some of the important statistical parameters are given in Table 2. The present results are comparable with those reported in the literature for L-proline (Table 3).

Effect of systematic errors on best-fit model :

In order to have a cognizance of the effects of errors in concentrations of ingredients (mineral acid, ligand, metal and alkali) on the stability constants of binary metal complexes, some representative systems were studied by introducing the errors in the concentrations of ingredients. These results (Table 4) emphasize that errors in the concentrations of alkali and acid affect more than other factors. With the introduction of errors, the standard deviations were found to increase, inferring the appropriateness of experimental conditions and correctness of analytical concentrations.

Effect of solvent :

PG is an amphiprotic and coordinating solvent. It is a

Fig. 1. Formation curves of metal-proline complexes in 30% v/v PG-water mixtures : (A) Co^{II} , (B) Ni^{II} , (C) Cu^{II} ; ligand concentrations in mmols are; (\square) 0.250, (\circ) 0.375, (Δ) 0.500.

Table 1. Exhaustive modeling of Co^{II} -proline complexes in 40% v/v PG-water mixture

Model number	pH range = 1.8–9.6; Number of points = 100			$U_{\text{corr}} \times 10^8$	χ^2	Skewness	Kurtosis	R-factor
	log β_{mlh} (SD)							
	ML	ML_2	MLH					
1	5.64(18)	-	-	7.31	92.00	0.50	7.53	0.0142
2	-	9.73(9)	-	3.77	87.63	-0.84	3.96	0.0102
3	-	-	12.42(42)	45.71	468.91	0.22	13.96	0.0356
4	5.31(12)	9.62(12)	-	2.63	98.40	-1.18	4.69	0.0085
5	-	10.00(8)	12.55(9)	2.71	83.57	-0.46	5.18	0.0086
6	5.88(17)	-	12.58(13)	6.11	152.21	0.97	10.31	0.0129
7	5.57(9)	9.86(9)	12.57(6)	1.42	69.71	-0.17	4.30	0.0062

$U_{\text{corr}} = U/(\text{NP} - m)$; m = number of species; NP = number of experimental points; SD = standard deviation.

Table 4. Effect of errors in influential parameters on the stability constants of Co^{II}-proline binary complexes in 40% v/v PG-water mixture

Ingredient	%	log β _{mlh} (SD)		
		ML	ML ₂	MLH
Alkali	Error			
	0	5.57(9)	9.86(9)	12.57(6)
	-5	4.07(36)	7.03(62)	Rejected
	-2	4.82(15)	8.61(17)	Rejected
	+2	6.56(8)	11.30(8)	13.21(4)
Acid	+5	10.56(8)	15.99(17)	13.61(10)
	-5	Rejected	Rejected	Rejected
	-2	6.92(8)	11.61(9)	13.65(4)
	+2	4.83(17)	8.70(18)	Rejected
	+5	4.14(47)	7.34(62)	Rejected
Ligand	-5	5.34(8)	9.70(8)	11.13(75)
	-2	5.48(8)	9.79(8)	12.31(8)
	+2	5.67(9)	9.93(10)	12.78(5)
	+5	5.82(9)	10.05(10)	13.03(5)
	Metal	-5	5.60(10)	10.01(9)
-2		5.58(9)	9.92(9)	12.59(6)
+2		5.56(8)	9.80(8)	12.56(6)
+5		5.54(8)	9.71(9)	12.54(6)
log F		-5	5.76(10)	10.05(10)
	-2	5.65(9)	9.94(10)	12.73(6)
	+2	5.50(8)	9.79(8)	12.41(7)
	+5	5.41(8)	9.70(8)	12.08(11)

Fig. 2. Variation of stability constant values of metal-proline complexes with reciprocal of dielectric constant (1/D) of PG-water mixtures : (A) Co^{II}, (B) Ni^{II}, (C) Cu^{II}; (□) log β_{ML}, (○) log β_{ML₂}, (Δ) log β_{MLH}.

Complex equilibria and distribution diagrams :

L-Proline has one dissociable carboxyl proton and one amino group which can associate with a proton. L-Proline exists as LH₂⁺, LH and L⁻ in the pH ranges 1.5–3.5, 3.0–10.0 and 9.0–11.0 respectively²⁹. Therefore, the stoichiometric coefficients of metal-ligand complexes of L-proline will depend on the pH range of study. The species that are refined are ML, ML₂ and MLH for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}. The stability constants of these species are found to follow the trend Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II}. This is in conformity with the Irving-Williams order³⁰. The additional high stability of Cu^{II} complex may be due to 3d⁹ electronic configuration. It acquires additional stabilization due to Jahn-Teller distortion.

ML and ML₂ species were reported in the literature^{17–23} for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}. But the present study reports MLH species also. The formation of various binary complex species is represented in the following equilibria :

The species distribution diagrams of various systems are shown in Fig. 3. MLH, ML and ML₂ species are formed in the pH range 3.0–9.5 and their percentages increase in the same order. For all metal-ligand systems, MLH species is formed by the interaction of metal ion with LH₂ (Equilibrium 1), because the percentages of metal ion and LH₂ are decreasing with increasing percentage of MLH. ML species can be formed by the deprotonation of MLH (Equilibrium 2), the interaction of metal ion with LH₂ (Equilibrium 3) and the interaction of metal ion with LH (Equilibrium 4). Equilibria 2 and 4 are more predominant than equilibrium 3 because the concentrations of metal ion, MLH and LH are decreasing with increasing concentration of ML. Equilibrium 3 is responsible for the initial formation of ML. The simultaneous formation of ML and ML₂ suggests the existence of both Equilibria 4 and 5. ML₂ is formed by the interaction of metal

Fig. 3. Distribution diagrams of binary complexes of proline in 30% v/v PG-water mixture : (A) Co^{II} , (B) Ni^{II} and (C) Cu^{II} .

ion with LH (Equilibrium 5), MLH with LH (Equilibrium 6) and ML with LH (Equilibrium 7). The first two equilibria are more appropriate because the concentrations of metal ion, MLH and LH are decreasing where ML_2 species is increasing.

Structures of complexes :

Bidentate or tridentate amino acids form octahedral metal-amino acid complexes³¹⁻³³. Depending upon the nature of the ligands and metal ions and based on the basic chemical knowledge, tentative structures of the complexes are proposed in Fig. 4. Carboxyl oxygen and amino nitrogen of L-proline are bonded to the metal ions. Amino nitrogen can associate with hydrogen ions in physiological pH ranges. Hence there is often significant competition between hydrogen and metal ion for this donor site and it results in the formation of protonated species.

Experimental

Materials and solutions :

1,2-Propanediol (Qualigens, India) was used as received. Aqueous solutions of L-proline (SRL, India), Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} chlorides (Qualigens, India) were prepared in triple-distilled water by maintaining 0.05 mol L^{-1} hy-

Fig. 4. Proposed structures of L-proline complexes, where S is either solvent or water molecules.

drochloric acid concentration to increase the solubility. The strengths of acid and alkali were determined using Gran plot method³⁴. To assess the errors that might have crept in to the determination of the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification (ANOVA)³⁵.

Apparatus :

The titrimetric data were obtained with a calibrated Systronics MK-VI digital pH meter which can monitor the changes in H^+ concentration. The pH meter was calibrated with potassium hydrogen phthalate (0.050 mol L^{-1}) in acidic region and borax (0.010 mol L^{-1}) solution in basic region. The glass electrode was equilibrated in a well stirred PG-water mixture containing inert electrolyte for several days. All the titrations were carried out in the medium containing varying compositions of PG (0.0-60.0% v/v) maintaining an ionic strength of 0.160 mol L^{-1} with sodium chloride at $303.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ K}$. The effects of variations in asymmetry potential, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error and dissolved carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode were accounted for in the form of correction factor³⁶.

Procedure :

For the determination of stability constants of metal-ligand binary species, initially titrations of strong acid with alkali were carried out at regular intervals to check whether complete equilibrium was achieved. Then the

calomel electrode was refilled with PG-water mixture of equivalent composition as that of titrand. Titrations with different ratios (1 : 2.5, 1 : 3.75, 1 : 5.0) of metal-to-ligand were carried out with 0.40 mol L⁻¹ sodium hydroxide. Other experimental details are given elsewhere³⁷.

Modeling strategy :

The computer program SCPHD³⁸ was used to calculate the correction factor. By using the pH-metric titration data, the binary stability constants were calculated with the computer program, MINQUAD75³⁹, which exploits the advantage of constrained least-squares method in the initial refinement and reliable convergence of Marquardt algorithm. The correction factor and protonation constants of L-proline were fixed during the refinement of binary systems.

Conclusions :

- (i) The common species formed due to the interaction of L-proline with the metals are ML, MLH and ML₂.
- (ii) Protonated species are formed at lower pH than the unprotonated species.
- (iii) The linear variation of stability constants as a function of mole fraction of the medium indicates the dominance of electrostatic forces over non-electrostatic forces. A linear increasing trend with increasing 1,2-propanediol content supports the predominance of the structure forming nature of PG over its complexing ability.
- (iv) The order of ingredients influencing the magnitudes of stability constants due to incorporation of errors in their concentrations is acid > alkali > ligand > log *F* > metal.
- (v) The stability constants of binary complexes are found to follow the trend Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II}.

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